

administrative work; 5.7% went into teaching and training; 4.7% into extension; 4% into writing for publication; and 2.2% into other activities. *W*

Genetic potential and utilization of rice in northeastern India

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Rices grown in northeastern India were collected to determine what germ plasm is available there and its potential. The rices were grown in a randomized block at the botanical garden of North Eastern Hill University, Shillong, and the mean height, yield, grain fineness, seed protein content, and protein yield per plant were determined. Three replications of 30 plants/replication per genotype were used. The mean values computed for various traits are depicted in Figures 1 and 2. The average shoot height of the rices ranged from 71 to 102 cm. Kba Saw rut B-2, Dullo-X, and Lyngri were the tallest varieties, with shoot heights of 102, 101, and 101 cm, respectively. Theuru red was the shortestest, 71 cm. Most of the rices were coarse-grained. Kba Saw rut B-2 had the finest grains and Lyngri, the coarsest.

The rices varied greatly in yield. Abar-B yielded highest followed by Ryllowhite. Local Beach-A yielded lowest. The crude seed protein content varied similarly. The highest protein level, 12.7%, was in Theuru red; the lowest, in Abar-B. But Abar-B had the best seed protein production per plant, closely followed by Ryllowhite. Fortunately, these two varieties have other desirable traits such as medium height, medium tillering, and heavy grain weight. Abar-B seems to be the best because of its high grain number per panicle, grain yield, and tiller production, along with its seed protein production. Abar-B also has high consumer preference and is well-adapted to the region's varying soil types and prevalent climatic conditions.

Furthermore, most of the inhabitants of the Northeastern Himalayan region are tribal people who are nonvegetarian, so

1. Performance of rice varieties: 1 = Abar-A, 2 = Abar-B, 3 = Abar red-A, 4 = Abar red-B, 5 = Ryllo red-1, 6 = Ryllo red-3, 7 = Ryllo red-4, 8 = Ryllo red-5, 9 = Ryllo red-6, 10 = Ryllowhite, 11 = Dullo-A, 12 = Dullo-6, 13 = Dullo-8, 14 = Dullo-X, 15 = Dullo XI, 16 = Kba Saw rut B-2, 17 = Kba Saw rut B-4, 18 = Nanglwai, 19 = Local Beach-A, 20 = Kuki, 21 = Theuru red, 22 = Lyngri, 23 = Keiba Thangamaa 24 = Tangla

2. Seed protein content and production. Kurukshetra University, India. (For names of varieties, see caption of Figure 1.)

Abar-B's comparatively lower seed protein would not be detrimental to growth and development. Thus Abar-B can safely be recommended for extensive cultivation and large-scale consumption in this region. ❧

Intan – a blast-resistant semidwarf rice for Karnataka, India

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Intan was an experimental line from Indonesia in a set of more than 1,000 rices screened for blast resistance at the Agricultural Research Station, Ponnampet, by scientists of the University of Agricultural Sciences in collaboration with the All-India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project and IRRI. In the kharif seasons of 1969 and 1970, Intan emerged as resistant to blast. Its other special features included intermediate height, improved plant type, late maturity, and fine grain quality. It was tested in the state coordination multilocation variety trials from 1971 to 1973 at Ponnampet, Mercara, Sirsi, and Mugad and on a private farm at Mudigere where no paddy could thrive due to severe blast. Intan was compared with popular local varieties KB 356, BKB, T141, Y 4, Puttabhatha, and the new varieties IR8, IR20, Pankaj, Jagannath, Mahsuri, Vijaya, and Manohansali. Not only was the resistance of Intan confirmed, it also yielded from 20 to 30% higher than the others. The yield increase was enormous in situations where blast was severe.

District trials were conducted in farmers' fields during 1973 in 0.4-ha (1-acre) plots to compare Intan with varieties such as KB 356, Puttabhatha, IE 20, S 701, Jaya, Hanagal Rajohog, and S 1092. The yield increase ranged from 4 to 37%, averaging 20%, even under submanagement situations. In 1974 and 1975, Intan yielded as high as 7.5 t/ha.

In 1975 the State Variety Evaluation Committee released Intan for commercial cultivation in the valleys of the hilly region. In 1977 the Committee recommended it for cultivation in the

lowlands of the direct-seeded tract. More than 12 ha of Intan were drill-sown in paddy block demonstrations organized by the State Department of Agriculture in Hassan District and were a great success.

Intan is photosensitive and grows to 100–125 cm in plains or hills. It grows fairly tall in coastal climate. The stems and leaves have purple pigmentation, which varies in intensity with altitude and season. The panicle is dense and partially droopy, bearing medium-slender, apiculus, and pigmented grains. It matures in 160–175 days. The CFTRI, Mysore, has reported that this rice is ideally suited for parboiling. Other reported merits are suitability to waterlogged conditions; good

performance even under low fertility levels; higher brown rice recovery and grain storage quality; less milling breakage; and tolerance to short-duration floods.

Intan has been well accepted by farmers in the hilly and direct-seeded regions of Karnataka. A successful ratoon crop was raised, producing about 2 t/ha with no fertilizers and with limited seepage water, at the Agricultural Research Station, Mercara. Some farmers have also reported ratooning Intan. The variety is capable of replacing any lowland late-maturing type and is ideally suited for blast-endemic areas. Even in the plains of Mysore and Hassan districts, Intan has replaced late local types such as S 1092 and S 749 and is spreading fast. ❧

Comparison of farmers' conditions, scientists' breeding efforts, and latest varieties

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IRRI attempted to obtain a measure of the relevance of scientists' research efforts in providing the types of varieties that farmers need in a study of rice breeding programs conducted in collaboration with Iowa State University, USA, and partially funded by the Rockefeller Foundation.

Each of 23 rice breeders at 22 experiment stations and universities in 8 Asian countries was asked 3 questions:

1) What percentage of the rice grown in farmers' fields within the area served by that experiment station was irrigated, rainfed lowland, upland, and deep-water or floating rice?

2) What percentage of the scientist's professional time was spent in

improvement of irrigated, rainfed lowland, upland, and deep-water or floating rice?

3) What percentage of all varieties released by that station over the past 5 years was suited for each of the 4 rice-growing conditions? To eliminate bias, the sequence of the three questions was dispersed among other questions in the survey.

The breeders perceived a mean of 43% of the rice grown on farmers' fields as irrigated. They spent a mean of 60% of their time working on irrigated rice and considered 57% of all varieties released by their stations over the previous 5 years as suitable for irrigated conditions (see table). Although 40% of the farmers' fields were cited as rainfed lowland, the scientists spent 22% of their time in that area and considered 32% of the recently released varieties suitable for rainfed conditions. Upland rice occupied

Rice breeders' perceptions of the rice-growing conditions in farmers' fields in the regions served by experiment stations, the mean percentages of research efforts that rice breeders devote to rices for those conditions, and the varieties released over the past 5 years. Twenty-three rice breeders for 23 regions served by 22 agricultural experiment stations and universities in 8 Asian nations, 1975.

Item	Irrigated	Rice-growing condition (%)		
		Rainfed lowland	Upland	Deep-water or floating
Farmers' fields	43	40	12	5
Scientists' research efforts	60	22	14	4
Newest varieties ^a	57	32	10	2

^a Released over the past 5 years